

Eye Tracking to GeoAI for Context-Aware, Personalized Geospatial Experiences

Merve Keskin*

* Department of Geoinformatics (Z_GIS), University of Salzburg, merve.keskin@plus.ac.at

Abstract

Eye tracking offers rich behavioral signals for training GeoAI models that adapt maps to users' tasks, capabilities, and situational context. I present a vision and foundational work towards gaze-based, context-aware cartography powered by eye tracking, behavioral metrics, and AI models. This work ranges from calibration-free, hands-free web map interaction using smooth pursuit and alternative modalities such as head and nose tracking, enabling gaze-controlled map operations such as pan, zoom, and select, to leveraging candidate indicators of search strategy and task success (e.g., Hit Any AOI Rate (HAAR) and Time to First Fixation (TTFF)) for user grouping. These metrics form state and reward signals for Long Short-Term Memory (LSTMs) networks, temporal convolutional networks (TCN), and reinforcement learning agents that learn to predict user intent and optimize map configuration in real time, advancing human-centered GeoAI for personalized geospatial experiences.

Keywords: context-aware maps, eye tracking, gaze-based interaction, HCI, geoAI

1. Motivation

Eye tracking provides essential human-attention signals for training GeoAI models, specifically sequential architectures like Long Short-Term Memory (LSTMs) networks and reinforcement learning (RL), that can be used in developing context-aware maps tailored to who (user characteristics and accessibility needs), where (location and spatial context), when (temporal dynamics), and how users interact with space (interaction modality and heuristics) supporting task-relevant, user- and location-specific, and real-time cartographic experiences. In contrast to using high-resolution eye trackers, scalable and low-cost implementations that utilize off-the-shelf (passive) cameras such as webcams and smartphone cameras exemplify how gaze can be collected at a larger scale (e.g., browser-based online user studies such as Afifah et al., 2025;

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Gharibpour Poshtiri, 2025; Vaníček et al., 2025) and can be transformed into training data for geospatial foundation models and personalized cartography. Because these implementations operate passively in the web browser without dedicated hardware, they lower both the cost and the participant burden of large-scale behavioral data collection, which is a prerequisite for training the sequential models and RL agents described in the sections that follow.

2. Vision: Gaze-Based Context-Aware Maps & Personalized Geo-Experiences

My overarching vision is to develop gaze-based context-aware maps that adapt to users in real time by integrating eye tracking and other modalities such as gestures, speech, mouse, keyboard, head or nose tracking (e.g., Tumenjargal, 2025) with measurable behavioral, contextual, and open-source environmental data. This vision extends into a broader “sensing human, sensing environment and personalizing geo-experiences” framework that fuses objective body and location data through wearables such as eye trackers, EDA sensors and GPS signals with subjective self-reports to model not only maps and map use but also sense of place (e.g., Moser et al., 2025). Within this framework, GeoAI models trained on multi-modal signals including RL for real-time adaptation can be paired with post-hoc explainability methods (e.g., attention rollout (Abnar et al., 2020), SHAP) to surface saliency information about which urban features drive predictions, how they are encoded, and how they modulate psychophysiological responses

3. Previous Foundational Research

Previous work demonstrated that traditional eye tracking reveals fixation patterns, saccadic behavior, and spatial processing strategies across maps (e.g., Keskin et al., 2023), while webcam eye tracking (i.e., WebGazer.js (Papoutsaki et al., 2016)) replicate lab-grade attention patterns from map memorability experiments (i.e., CartoGAZE dataset (Keskin, 2023)), when using larger AoIs and appropriate calibration thresholds, as validated by CartoGAZEweb dataset (Gharibpour, 2025a). Despite significantly lower resolution (~20–30 Hz vs. ~250 Hz for infrared eye trackers), online webcam eye tracking experiments still yield reliable gaze metrics for coarse attentional modeling and task analysis (Gharibpour, 2025b). To make such labeled empirical data accessible and useful for training GeoAI models, Keskin et al. (2025) developed MAPVERSE (<https://github.com/MAP-VERSE/repository>) to, an open metadata repository that curates map usability datasets (eye tracking, mouse tracking, EEG, and other modalities) and formalizes validity dimensions (i.e., controlled conditions, tasks and research questions, metrics, stimuli, participant characteristics, and ethics) qualify as benchmark datasets. As part of Awesome Public Datasets (<https://github.com/awesomedata/awesome-public-datasets>), MAPVERSE provides a structured, searchable interface for discovering gaze datasets across in-lab, online, XR, and real-world experiments, with a strong emphasis on reproducibility.

4. Current Foundation Research

Regular internet use in the EU is still significantly lower for people with severe disabilities, especially upper limbic impairments, than for those without (Eurostat, 2025), and many users, disabled or not, experience hand and wrist pain from intensive device use (McLaughlin et al., 2023). This underscores the need for alternative, hands-free interaction techniques, especially for

web maps, as they are among the most frequently visited services on the internet and demand active interaction from end users. At the same time, current webcam eye tracking calibration procedures are typically long and tedious (e.g., Realeye.io’s 39-point process), causing high dropout rates. Improving the accessibility of web maps for users with limited motor abilities and preventing low participation due to lengthy calibration motivated us to develop a browser-based, calibration-free and hands-free web map prototype using WebGazer.js. We demonstrated that smooth pursuit eye movements (Esteves et al., 2015), which are the slow, continuous tracking of moving object, and not bounded by the gaze estimation accuracy, enable gaze-based pan, zoom, and selection interactions without explicit calibration (Tumenjargal, 2025). This prototype serves as a testbed for data collection so that GeoAI models can learn user intent from gaze trajectories to drive adaptive interface changes.

As intention and task prediction play an important role in map personalization and providing interventions to optimize geovisualization, we have developed strategies to group map users purely based on their gaze behavior. In our preliminary analysis of the CartoGAZE dataset, Hit Any AOI Rate (HAAR) (Wang et al., 2022) and Time to First Fixation (TTF) emerged as the most effective behavioral separators, showing greater differentiation across user groups than demographic labels such as gender and expertise. HAAR-based grouping (high: 96–100, moderate: 75–95, exploratory: 50–75, low: <50) revealed high-HAAR users showed structured, goal-oriented search with dense fixation clusters on task-relevant AOIs, many short saccades, TTF <1s in 7s trials, and efficient AOI transitions, whereas low-HAAR users showed scattered patterns with many long saccades, delayed first fixations, and frequent visits to irrelevant regions (Ramdas, 2025). Such metrics can serve as states or rewards in a reinforcement learning framework: high-HAAR, low-TTF, short-saccade patterns indicate successful, intention-aligned guidance, while low-HAAR, long-saccade patterns can trigger adaptations such as additional guidance, simplified visuals, or alternative task suggestions. Modeling these gaze sequences such as fixation series, saccade transitions, and AOI visit patterns calls for the following candidate architectures suited to temporal, sparse behavioral data: (i) LSTMs (Cornia et al., 2018) and temporal convolutional networks (TCN) (Sobrian et al., 2024) for fixation sequence modeling and eye movement classification; (ii) graph attention networks (Hartley, 2024) for encoding AOI transition graphs; (iii) gaze-conditioned transformer encoders (Ryan et al., 2025) or graph neural networks (Özdel et al., 2024) for learning task-intent representations. These behavioral representations produced by these sequential models, when validated on large volumes of map use data and through repeated interaction, can inform RL agents to decide how and when the system should modify the map configuration (scale, symbolization, interaction mode) or intervene in response to observed heuristics in real time (Khamaj et al., 2024).

5. GeoAI Contributions and Future Directions

Together with prior and ongoing projects on user grouping based on gaze patterns, integration of behavioral and contextual data, and evaluation of gaze-based context-aware maps, the proposed vision, including data and model foundation (Phase 1) and deployment and adaptation (Phase 2), advances from theory to predictive AI models (Figure 1). This vision positions eye tracking as a behavioral data source for geospatial foundation models, enabling them to learn what users’ attention is focused on, in which contexts, and with which cognitive efforts. By contributing metadata repositories for empirical data and AI-ready labels, we can create an infrastructure for training and benchmarking GeoAI methods on realistic, task-driven map stimuli. However,

scaling gaze and physiological signal collection raises significant ethical and privacy considerations because these data encode sensitive cognitive and potentially biometric information. We, therefore, should emphasize informed consent, data anonymization, and ethics-aware metadata practices (e.g., in MAPVERSE), and align future deployments with regulations such as GDPR. Finally, this approach advances accessible and human-centered GeoAI by grounding model training in empirically validated behavioral data rather than relying solely on participatory design or self-report measures which operationalize human-centeredness through objective, task-driven evidence of how people actually use maps.

Figure 1. Proposed vision for adaptive maps (Created with assistance from Claude Sonnet 4.6, Anthropic.)

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